

DEMAND FOR RESPONSIBLE TOURISM IN SRI LANKA: A CASE STUDY OF
YALA WILDLIFE DESTINATION

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Abstract: The objective of this study is to analyse the demand for responsible tourism in Sri Lanka by identifying the key factors affecting demand for responsible tourism. Such contributory factors are analysed to determine the degree of influence for the demand. Given the size and numerous stakeholders in the industry, the scope of this study was limited to analysing international tourists' demand for responsible tourism in the Yala Wildlife Destination. In order to understand the key factors influencing demand for responsible tourism, a comprehensive review of literature was conducted. Findings from the literature review that conditions in the tourism destination, demographic factors, concern for local communities, and pricing in the destination market are the main factors influencing demand for responsible tourism. Based on these key findings from the literature review, the conceptual framework and the hypotheses of the study were developed. Conceptual framework of the study consisted of four independent variables i.e. Concern for local communities in the tourism destination, conditions in the tourism destination, demographic factors, and pricing in the tourism destination, and one dependent variable i.e. demand for responsible tourism in Yala Wildlife Destination. Data for the study was obtained from a structured self-administered questionnaire, which was distributed to international tourists visiting hotels located in the Yala Wildlife Destination. Bivariate analysis of survey data indicated that all four independent variables have statistically significant correlations with the dependent variable (demand) in the model. Multivariate analysis of the data indicated that the four independent variables collectively accounts for 94.8% of the variance in the dependent variable.

Keywords: Responsible Tourism, Sri Lanka Tourism, Factors Of Demand for Tourism, Wildlife

Introduction

Yala Wildlife Destination which has been a perennial favourite for tourists over the years, has seen a spike in visitors since the end of the civil war in 2009. This destination recorded its highest number of visitors in 2017 with a total 604,678 visiting it during the year. Out of the 604,678 tourists who visited the park, 314,609 were local tourists and 290,069 were foreign tourists. This high number of visitors has had both a positive and negative impact on the destination. In terms of positive effects, the large number of visitors to the destination has resulted in revenues of the park, and the tourist establishments in the area increasing exponentially. For example, the Yala national park which is located within this destination earned a revenue of Rs.669.83 million in 2017, the highest ever revenue earned by a national park in Sri Lanka. Negative effects to the destination include the negative impact to the flora and fauna of the destination on account of the large number of visitors to the area.

The damage caused to the destination is likely to intensify further in the future on account of projected exponential growth in the number of local and international tourists visiting this destination. This in turn will have a negative impact on key stakeholders such as hotels, restaurants, small scale vendors, park guides, safari operators, etc., who depend on the Yala Wildlife Destination for their income and livelihood. The Main research question is 'What are the major contributing factors for responsible tourism demand in Sri Lanka?' and Overall objective of the study is 'To analyse the contributing factors for the demand of responsible

tourism in Sri Lanka with special reference to Yala Wildlife Destination' the specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine key factors driving the demand for responsible tourism in Sri Lanka.
2. To possible benefits to community stakeholders from responsible tourism demand.

Literature Review

Responsible Tourism

Responsible tourism which is defined as “making better places for people to live in and better places for people to visit” (Responsible Tourism, 2016) can be segmented into different types based on two codes i.e. the Globe Code of Ethics for Responsible Tourism developed by the UNWTO and the Principles of Responsible Tourism outlined in the Declaration of Cape Town in 2002. Of these two codes, the latter is considered extremely important, as it has been ratified by all stakeholders in the global tourism industry. The key principles of responsible tourism outlined in the Cape Town Declaration (<https://responsibletourismpartnership.org>) include the following:

1. Minimises negative economic, environmental, and social impacts
2. Generates greater economic benefits for local people and enhances the well-being of host communities, improves working conditions and access to the industry
3. Involves local people in decisions that affect their lives and life chances
4. Makes positive contributions to the conservation of natural and cultural heritage, to the maintenance of the world's diversity
5. Provides more enjoyable experiences for tourists through more meaningful connections with local people, and a greater understanding of local cultural, social and environmental issues
6. Provides access for physically challenged people
7. Culturally sensitive, engenders respect between tourists and hosts, and builds local pride and confidence

Goodwin (2011, p.125) describes responsible tourism as “taking responsibility for achieving sustainable development through tourism...it is about identifying economic, social, and environmental issues which matter locally and tackling them”. Further, according to this researcher, responsible tourism is not a separate isolated form of tourism, as it connects with all forms of human activity, and evolves according to the evolving needs and attitudes of all stakeholders in the industry. Responsible tourism is defined by the Centre for responsible Travel (2009, p.12) as “creating a better destination through conservation and protection”, whilst Spence et al (2002) defines it as “benefitting local communities”.

Perspectives of Responsible Tourism

The need for a more responsible form of tourism is a subject which has been debated and researched extensively (Krippendorf, 1987). This concept that key actors or stakeholders in the tourism industry should behave in an ethical manner which extends beyond petty narcissist interest has gained significant attention over last couple decades on account of global warming and other environmental changes caused by human activity, particularly human economic activities. The main focus of interest in this regard has been based on understanding whether key tourism industry stakeholders are concerned about the consequences of their actions, if these concerns have translated into these stakeholders behaving in a more responsible manner, and the opportunities and threats to stakeholders on account of making responsible tourism decisions and choices (Budeanu, 2007).

Other research pertaining to responsible tourism posits that the growing interest in ethical tourism consumption is influenced by a collapse in perceived alternatives to capitalism, and an increasing rejection of the traditional politics of social class and political parties. This context encourages more people to focus on their own individual actions at the level of their everyday consumption in order to express their beliefs and aspirations for social change. Research conducted by Butcher (2003) in this regard identified 'lifestyle politics' as a key factor which has the potential to make a significant difference on floor level of responsible tourism. Further, Butcher (2003) states the tourism industry tunnel focus on individuality and consumption, instead of collective responses and production, has resulted in limitations and weaknesses of responsible tourism as a political strategy.

Another perspective pertaining to responsible tourism is the political assumptions behind the analysis. Some researchers in this area postulate that it is more effective to focus on achieving small-scale improvements within capitalists societies, than attempting to make challenging and time-consuming fundamental changes. This perspective of making small incremental changes has been challenged by some researchers who argue that in order to accomplish substantial improvements it is essential to impose radical challenges and critiques on society. Research conducted by Duffy (2015) in regard, concluded that certain radical challenges and critiques to established economic, political, and social norms have facilitated the development of ecotourism in Madagascar.

However, Duffy (2015) cautions against reading too much into this finding, by stating that ecotourism is not the magic elixir for responsible tourism, but merely an expansion of global neo-liberalism. In contrast to the suggestions of Duffy (2015), Higgins-Desbiolles (2006) argues for a 'radical' rather than a 'reformist' position, and this appears to entail rethinking our ideas about responsibility in tourism due to the constraints on agency in our daily lives, that need to be addressed through political action. This radical position entails ethical and political challenges to the inequalities of capitalist society, and its capitalist-driven consumption. Higgins-Desbiolles terms this approach as 'justice tourism'.

Influence of Responsible Tourism on Consumers

Research studies indicate that consumer demand for responsible tourism is increasing. A research study on responsible tourism conducted by the UNWTO in 2012 reported that "tourists' choices are increasingly influenced by sustainability considerations" (UNWTO, 2012), whilst according to Bricker (2012) "sustainable tourism is becoming more widely accepted – so much so that the United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), now believes that it will go from 'alternate' to 'mainstream' tourism within a decade". Tip (nd) numerous surveys and statistics over the recent past indicate a strong consumer shift towards responsible tourism, and responsible tourism organizational practices. For example, a sustainable tourism survey conducted by the organization Blue and Green Tomorrow (2014) found that 43% of the respondents interviewed were extremely concerned about the impact or footprint their holiday has on the environment and society in the tourism destination, whilst 10% of the respondents express partial concern for the impact their holiday has on the environment and society in the tourism destination. In addition, a wire survey conducted by Bricker in 2012 reported that 66% of consumers from around the world expressed a strong preference to buy products and services from organizations that implemented sustainable practices, which are focused on giving back to society (Bricker, 2012).

Key Factors Influencing Consumer Preference for Responsible Tourism

Concerns by the responsible tourists for wellbeing of local communities and conservation of their natural and cultural resources on tourism development: Findings from the literature indicate that concern for local communities and the environment are one of the main factors driving consumer demand for responsible tourism. Research conducted by Goodwin and Francis (2003) in this regard found that two out three (71%) British and Australian travellers, and over half (53%) of U.S. travellers, endorse the protection of destination communities' wellbeing and culture.

International tourists concern and support for local communities driving demand for responsible tourism is also supported by findings from a survey conducted by IHEI (2002) on tourism in the United Kingdom. This survey found that 76% of British tourists felt that it is important that their trip to benefit the people living at the destination, up from 71% in 2000. Concern and support for local communities driving demand for responsible tourism is also underscored by research conducted by Tearfund (2000). Findings from this research study revealed that 62% of Australian, 57% of British, and 49% of U.S tourists' selected tourism destinations, hotels, etc., which had invested in the development of local community businesses, education, and health services. Hence:

Hypothesis H1: Concerns by the responsible tourists for wellbeing of local communities and conservation of their natural and cultural resources on tourism development

Tourism Destination Influence of Demand for Responsible Tourism

In terms of the tourism destinations, findings from empirical research indicate that two domains i.e. destination attractiveness and the development of tourism infrastructure are key factors influencing tourism demand. In terms of the destination attractiveness, a key factor which influences destination attractiveness is the number of UNESCO sites in the destination (Cuiluc, 2014), whilst in terms of tourism infrastructure, key factors which influence tourism demand is accommodation capacity in the destination (Khadaroo and Seetanah, 2007). In addition to the development of tourism infrastructure, findings from empirical research indicate that the development of the overall infrastructure of the country is essential for the growth in tourism demand. Investigating the importance of inbound country infrastructure on tourism arrivals, Khadaroo and Seetanah (2007) concluded that development of traffic infrastructure (measured by the net investment in land, air and sea infrastructure) has an impact on arrivals of tourists from other countries, whilst development of other types of infrastructure i.e. water supply, sewerage, and electricity are not as important.

Hypothesis H2: Conditions in tourism destination market influences demand for responsible tourism in Yala wildlife destination.

Demographic Factors Influence on Demand for Responsible Tourism

Findings from the literature review reveal that demographic factors such as age, marital status, social class, gender, family cycle, and household income have a significant influence on tourism demand. In terms of household income, research conducted by Dardis et al. (1981) investigated two income measures i.e. disposable income and total household expenditure income in this regard. The use of total expenditure has been defended on the basis of the permanent income hypothesis, and the fact that it is a better measurement of a household's permanent income, than disposable income, which is likely to fluctuate over a short period of time. Thus, Prais and Houthakker (1971) Fish and Waggle (1996), based on the findings from their research posit

that high-income families are likely to have significantly high holiday expenditure, than low, and middle- income families.

In terms of lifecycle, findings from the literature reveal that senior citizens continue to travel in ways comparable to their travel in younger years. Theories of aging, such as Atchley's (1989), suggest that individuals tend to sustain consistent patterns of behaviour, and are not prone to major shifts in likes, dislikes, and general activities. Research by Searle, Mactavish, and Brayley (1993) showed that patterns of leisure decision-making were consistent over life spans. Continuers are the term used by the researchers to refer to people who continue the pattern of leisure they established at an early stage of adult development.

In terms of age, findings from empirical research indicate that the age factor is expected to be a major determinant of leisure spending behaviour. Statistics from the Consumer Expenditure Survey (2000) on Travel Expenditures revealed a significant relationship between age of traveller and their expenditure patterns. In regard to numbers of trips taken, the highest percentage of trip takers were those in the age group 45 to 54 years, whilst the lowest were those in the age group 65 years and older. This group, however, had the highest average expenditures on trips of any of the age groups. It is interesting to note, that the group consisting mainly of retirees spent an average of 4% of total average annual expenditures on trips and vacations. This is about twice the share spent by most of the other age cohorts. However, the 65-and-older group did not account for the highest share of aggregate trip expenditures. That distinction went to the group age 35 to 44, followed by the 65-and older group at 19% with the groups ages 25 to 34 and 55 to 64 each accounting for 15%. The age group 25 years and below spent the least accounting for only 4% of total trip expenditures.

In terms of gender, findings from empirical research indicate that gender is not an important segmentation variable for the tourism industry (Lawson, 1991). However, men and women may travel with different purposes. Findings from research conducted by Walters (1988) revealed that even though men still dominate the business travel market, the same is not true for the leisure market, with women taking as many, and sometimes even more holidays than men (Collins and Tisdell, 2002).

Marital status is also another significant determinant of tourism demand. Findings from empirical research indicate that families which comprise only of husband and wife, and individuals who are single are more likely to take a vacation, than individuals who are married with children (Consumer Expenditure Survey, 2000). However, whilst couples without children, and unmarried individuals take more vacations than families, the aggregate expenditure of families (i.e. couples with children) is greater that of couples, and unmarried individuals (ibid). Findings from the Consumer Expenditure Survey also revealed that families with two parents are more likely to take vacations, than single parent families (ibid).

Social class in terms of education and occupation of an individual also has a significant impact on tourism demand. Dardis et al. (1981) found that education enhances many types of recreation activities such as foreign travel and tours. In addition, education may provide training and preparation for some types of recreation activities. The impact of education on broadening one's perspective towards leisure pursuits has been noted by Burdge (1969). Cai, Hong, and Morrison (1995) concluded that the amount of education a household head received has a positive relationship with the expenditures on travel and vacations. Additional research conducted by Cai (1998). Dardis et al. (1981) concluded that social class has a significant impact on recreation expenditures. Education is positively related to recreation expenditures while there are no definite trends with respect to occupation. Hence:

Hypothesis H3: Demographic profile of international tourist influences demand for responsible tourism at Yala wildlife destination.

Pricing Influence on Demand for Responsible Tourism

The most common variable which has been used as an explanatory variable for tourism demand is price. Price in this regard is defined by Lim (2006) as costs of goods and services for the tourists in the tourism destination. As per Durbarry and Sinclair (2003), price competitiveness is essential for the tourism destination to be competitive as it determines its share of international tourism pie. This importance of pricing as an explanatory variable for tourism demand contradicts the research of Witt and Witt (1995), which found that the main economic factors used as explanatory variables for tourism demand are Consumer Price Index (CPI), and effective interest rate. Findings from empirical research conducted by Simundic (2015) indicated that the correlation between proxy variables for price and tourism demand is negative.

In addition to prices and income, findings from the literature review indicate that costs have an inverse relationship with tourism demand i.e. as tourism costs increase, tourism demand declines. Whilst the theoretical assumptions of the negative correlation between costs and tourism demand have never been doubted, there is a dearth of research on this correlation on account of the unavailability of costs data (Habibi and Rahim, 2009). The positive correlation between the population in the tourism source market and tourism demand is also supported by findings from empirical research conducted by Amelung and Viner (2006), which identified population growth as one of the main influences of growth in the global tourism industry, and research conducted by Witt and Witt (2009), which found that generic growth as well as migration are significant influences of tourism demand. Hence,

Hypothesis H4: Pricing in the tourism source market influences demand for responsible tourism at Yala wildlife destination

The conceptual model of this study is shown in **Figure 1**. As shown in this figure, **responsible tourism** is the dependent variable and the main variable of interest in this study, whilst concern for local communities and conservation, conditions in the tourism destination market, demographic profile of international tourists, and pricing in the tourism source market are the independent variables. It is assumed in this conceptual model that there are statistically significant correlations between the independent variables and the dependent variable, and that individual and collective changes in the status of the independent variables influence changes in the dependent variable.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Methodology

Population and Sample

Population for the study consists of all international travellers visiting the Yala wildlife destination during the period July 2018 i.e. approximately 15,800 international visitors. Note, this figure is based on 2017 data which indicated that approximately 15,000 international visitors visited Yala wildlife destination in July, 2017. Sample size for the study was determined using a sample size calculator (Creative Research Systems, 2018). Confidence level and confidence interval used to determine the sample size was 95% and 5% respectively. Based on this confidence level and interval, sample size determined for a population of 15,000 was approximately 375.

A sample respondents was selected from ten resort hotels situated in Yala Wildlife Destination (**Table 1**). Note, the sample of respondents was selected from these ten resort hotels using a sample random sampling technique.

Table 1: Selection of Sample Respondents

Name of hotel	Number of respondents selected
Cinnamon Wild	37
Jetwing Yala	37
Chana Hut	37
The Yala Adventure	42
Diyadahara Resort	37
Saraya Village	37
Ruhunu Safari Camp	37
Thaulle Resorts	37
Leopard Trail	37
Elephant Reach Hotel	37
Total	375

The main data collection instrument used in this study was structured self-administered questionnaire consisting of 35 closed ended questions. Responses to these questions were in the form of a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Data Analysis and Findings

Quantitative data obtained from the questionnaire was analysed statistically. IBM's statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse the data statistically. Univariate analysis was used to analyse survey respondents' response to each question in the questionnaire, bivariate analysis was used to determine the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable in the study, whilst multivariate was used to determine the collective and individual effect of the independent variables on the dependent variables. In addition, Cronbach Alpha was used to test the internal reliability of the data. Findings from the data analysis are presented in the next chapter using simple table and figures. Internal consistency of data was analysed using Cronbach Alpha in SPSS, the alpha coefficient for the 25 items in the study is .987. This suggests that the **25 items** have relatively high levels of internal consistency.

Table 2.- Presentation of Findings from the Analysis of the Questionnaire

Marital Status	Single – 23%	Married – 63%	Other – 14%	
Age Profile	20-29 14%	30-39 23%	40-49 20%	Morethan49 43%
Employment	Employed- 78%	Retired- 22%		
Annual income \$	<5000 23%	5001-75001 17%	7501-10000 12%	>15000 48%

Table 2. shows the marital status of survey respondents. As shown a large percentage of the survey respondents are married (63%), followed by respondents who are single (23%), and those in the other category based on this analysis, it can be concluded that a large percentage of international tourists visiting the Yala Wildlife Destination are married, followed by those who are single.

The age profile of survey respondents is also shown in **Table 2.** As indicated a large percentage of survey respondents are over 49 years of age (43%), followed by those in the 30 years to 39 years age group (23%), respondents in the 40 years to 49 years age group (20%), and respondents in the 20 years to 29 years age group (14%). Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that most respondents visiting the Yala Wildlife Destination are over 30 years of age (86%).

The employment status of survey respondents is shown in **Table 2.** As indicated 78% of the respondents are employed, whilst the balance 22% are retired. Based on this analysis it can be concluded that most international tourists visiting the Yala Wildlife Destination are employed and have a regular source of income.

The annual income of survey respondents is shown in **Table 2.** As shown in this table, 48% of survey respondents annual income exceeds U.S.\$ 15,000, followed by respondents whose income is below U.S.\$ 5,000 (23%), respondents whose annual income is between U.S.\$ 5,001 to U.S.\$ 7,500 (17%), and respondents whose annual income is between U.S.\$ 7,501 to U.S.\$ 10,000 (12%). This analysis suggests that a large percentage of international tourists visiting Sri Lanka are high income individuals.

Table 3.- Presentation of Findings from the Analysis of Questionnaire

Indicator	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
Tourism impact on local communities (%)			17	46	37
Tourism impact on conservation on local communities(%)		6	12	46	36
Tourism impact concern on fauna in the Yala wild life destination (%)			8	43	49
Tourism impact on water and naturel resources at yala wild life destination (%)		5	20	29	46
Tourism impact about carbon foot print in the yala wild life destination (%)		3	16	32	49
Tourism impact pollution caused in the yala wild life destination (%)		3	25	12	60
Willing to pay more to support the development of local community (%)			5	49	46
Willing to pay more to invest in the preservation of the local flora & fauna (%)			5	29	66
Willing to pay more implement responsible tourism practices (%)			3	49	48
Enjoyed stay at yala wild life destination(%)			8	29	63
Intention to re visit yala wild life destination (%)	3	6	11	44	36
Recommend to others (%)			11	23	66
Promote other activities in yala wild life destination (%)			23	20	57

Survey respondents concern about the impact tourism has on local communities in the Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this table, a large percentage of the survey respondents are extremely concerned about the impact tourism has on local communities in the Yala Wildlife Destination. Survey respondents concern about the impact tourism has on the traditions of local communities is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this table, a large percentage of survey respondents are concerned about the impact (82%) tourism has on the traditions of local communities in the Yala Wildlife Destination. Survey respondents concern regarding the impact tourism has on the fauna in Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. Based on the data in this table, it can be inferred that survey respondents are extremely concerned about the impact tourism has on the fauna in the Yala Wildlife Destination. Survey respondents concern regarding the impact tourism has on the flora at Yala Wildlife Destination. Based on the data shown in this table, it can be concluded that survey respondents are concerned about the impact tourism has on the flora at Yala Wildlife Destination. Survey respondents concern about the impact tourism has on the water and other natural resources at

Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. Based on the data in this table, it can be concluded that survey respondents are concerned about the impact tourism has on the water and other natural resources at the Yala Wildlife Destination.

Survey respondents concern about the carbon footprint created by tourism in the Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. The data in this table suggests that survey respondents are concerned about the carbon footprint created by tourism in the Yala Wildlife Destination. Survey respondents concern about the pollution caused to the Yala Wildlife Destination by tourism is indicated in **Table 3**. Based on the data in this table, it can be concluded that the survey respondents are extremely concerned about the pollution caused to the Yala Wildlife Destination on account of tourism. Survey respondents' willingness to visit Yala Wildlife Destination if it supports the development of local communities is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, a large percentage of survey respondents are willing to pay more to visit Yala Wildlife Destination, if it supports the development of local communities. Survey respondents' willingness to pay more to visit the Yala Wildlife Destination if it invests in the preservation of the local fauna and flora is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, a large percentage of the survey respondents' are willing to pay more to visit the Yala Wildlife Destination if it invest in the preservation of the local fauna and flora.

Survey respondents' willingness to pay more to visit the Yala Wildlife Destination if tourists firms in the destination implement responsible tourism practices is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, a large percentage of the survey respondents' are willing to pay more to visit the Yala Wildlife Destination if tourists firms in the destination implement responsible tourism practices. The extent to which survey respondents' have enjoyed their stay at the Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, most of the survey respondents' have enjoyed their stay at Yala Wildlife Destination. Survey respondents' intention to revisit Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, 80% of survey respondents intend to revisit Yala Wildlife Destination. This high figure argues well for the long-term sustainability of the destination.

Survey respondents' intention to recommend the Yala Wildlife Destination to others is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, 89% of survey participants intend to recommend Yala Wildlife Destination to others. This high figure argues will for the long-term sustainability of the destination. Survey respondents' intention to actively promote the Yala Wildlife Destination is shown in **Table 3**. As indicated in this figure, 77% of survey participants intend to actively promote the Yala Wildlife Destination. This high figure argues will for the long-term sustainability of the destination.

Conclusion and Discussion

The main objective of this study was to analyse current international tourists' demand for responsible tourism at Yala Wildlife Destination. Findings from the data analysis indicated that demand for responsible tourism at Yala Wildlife Destination is extremely high with international tourists' willing to pay more to visit the destination if the tourism industry invests in protecting local communities, culture, fauna and flora, religions practices and beliefs, and the natural resources of the destination. Further findings from the data analysis indicated that 94.8% of demand for responsible tourism in the Yala Wildlife Destination is influenced by these four factors. Of these factors, findings from the data analysis indicated that conditions in the destination market is the main factors influencing demand for responsible tourism in the Yala Wildlife Destination, followed by price related factors, concern for the local environment, and demographic factors.

Recommendations

In order to improve tourism in the Yala Wildlife Destination the following should be implemented by the Government of Sri Lanka and other key stakeholders in the destination:

Improve conditions in the Yala Wildlife Destination: Stakeholders should focus on improving conditions in the Yala Wildlife Destination as findings indicate that this is a main factor influencing demand for responsible tourism. In this regard, particular attention should be spent on protecting the fauna and flora in the destination as findings indicate that international tourists are willing to spend more in the destination if some of these funds are invested in these areas. In order to protect the fauna and flora at Yala Wildlife Destination, the following measures should be implemented:

Limit entry of tourists to the destination: A limit should be established on the number of tourists to the destination. A maximum of 3,000 tourists a day should be permitted to enter some of the fragile ecosystems of the destination e.g. the Yala Wildlife Sanctuary.

Limit access to certain areas and regions in the destination: Tourists' entering the destination should only be allowed access to certain demarcated areas and regions of the destination.

Increase fines: Fines for polluting the environment should be increased exponentially in order to reduce the impact to the fauna and flora in the region from pollution.

Educate tourists: Tourists should be educated on the unique fauna and flora of the destination.

Recruit additional employees: Additional employees should be recruited to monitor and protect the fauna and flora in the area.

Implement community safe circle to protect the destination. Protect resources of the destination is key to attract more tourist to the destination. Poaching, cattle feeding, Illegal farming identified as major threat to the Yala wildlife destination. When implementing a community safe cycle with community participation and give them the responsibility to protect the buffer zone and national park it will be more effective to protect the destination and reduce illegal activities.

Reward staff and service providers. When rewarding the service providers and staff with their positive engagement it will be positive courage to join others with them for better service. Further in order to increase demand for responsible tourism, authorities should also focus on reducing the carbon footprint and pollution caused by tourism in the destination. In order to reduce the carbon footprint and pollution caused by tourism in the destination the following should be implemented:

Limit the number of automobiles entering sensitive ecosystems in the destination: The number of automobiles entering sensitive ecosystems in the destination should be limited. For example, a maximum of 200 vehicles should only be permitted to enter the Yala Wildlife Sanctuary on a daily basis.

Establish and enforce strict environmental protection regulations: Strict environmental protection regulations should be established and enforced for all tourism establishments operating in the destination. In addition, tourists' establishments in the region should be encouraged to invest in technology which reduces pollution. For example, hotels and other

large tourists, establishments in the destination should be encouraged to establish water treatment plants, use solar energy, etc., to reduce their carbon footprint.

Regulatory support: The Government of Sri Lanka and local authorities in the destination should support tourist establishments' efforts to implement green practices by providing soft loans, tax concessions, etc., for establishments in the area implementing green operating practices.

Ensure tourism development benefits local communities in the destination: The Government of Sri Lanka and local authorities in the Yala Wildlife Destination should ensure that local communities in the area benefit from the growth of tourism in the destination. In order to increase benefits to the local communities in the destination, the following should be implemented.

Invest tax and other income generated tourism in local communities: Regulatory authorities should ensure that some of the tax income generated from tourism is invested in the development of health, education, and other infrastructure of local communities.

Establish systems which enable local communities to directly benefit from tourism: In this regard, local communities in the destination should be educated on how to establish and operate AirBnB, facilities in their residences. Further, the Government of Sri Lanka, the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Tourism, etc., should provide technical and financial assistance for households in these local communities to establish AirBnB, facilities. Establishment of AirBnB, facilities will enable individuals and families in local communities in the Yala Wildlife Destination to directly benefit from tourism development in the area.

Encourage recruitment of individuals from local communities into the industry: Tourism regulatory authorities should encourage tourists' establishments in the destination to recruit employees from the local communities. Recruitment of individuals from these communities will facilitate the development of these local communities, and also benefit tourists, establishments as it will reduce the high cost e.g. accommodation, high salaries, etc., associated with recruiting individuals from outside areas.

Introduce tax reduction scheme for tourism establishment when buying community products and supporting the community: When tourism establishments buying local community product and their services authorities can apply a tax reduction scheme to encourage them to buy more community product for their value chain.

Encourage tourism establishment to promote community experience activities: Tourists' are looking for more valuable authentic lifetime experience in their holidays so when tourism establishment promotes community activities both parties will get benefits.

Reduce tourism leakages from the destination: When the tourism establishment uses imported items for their services income generated from the destination will leak out of the destination. If they can use maximum local products for their value chain, it will help remain the money in the destination and use the destination development.

When we consider all those factors, Sri Lanka has to consider more revenue generation with quality tourism rather than considering the quantity of tourist arrival that is the responsible way forward to the sustainability of Sri Lanka tourism.

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